

Supplementary Material for “Parallel Seeds: From Foundation Models to Foundation Intelligence for Agricultural Sustainability”

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SUPPLEMENTARY NOTE

I. CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES

In the physical space, Parallel Seeds gathers, authenticates and integrates all genetic elements of the crop, or the ‘words’ of the underlying unknown molecular language, as well as high-throughput micro- and macroscale phenotypes at spatio-temporal resolution. In the parallel cyber space, it constructs and trains FMLMs, and through extensive computational tests using FMLMs, it returns FI for interpreting the molecular language to reveal the causal relationships between genetic elements and phenotypes and prescribing breeding of elites in the physical space. Correspondingly, Parallel Seeds faces three major challenges, i.e., accurate genetic element selection (physical space), high-throughput phenotyping (physical space), and FM construction and training (cyber space). The development of genotyping and phenotyping is shown in Fig. S1.

A. Comprehensive genetic element selection

Genome carries the complete set of genetic material (DNA) present in an organism. Genome size of crop species can be large and variable, e.g., the haploid genome of rice is about 400 megabases (Mb) while that of wheat can reach 5000 Mb. At microscale, a crop system is thus characterized by non-linear interactions of large-scale genetic elements, which involves not only coding sequences or genes, elements regulating the expression of genes, but also non-coding sequences including highly abundant genomic repeats, mostly with unknown functions. In addition, varieties of a crop species usually carry single-nucleotide level and structural level variations to each other. These factors make the comprehensive collection of genetic elements extremely challenging.

Fig. S1. Development of genotyping and phenotyping. a. DNA, RNA and protein analysis at the era of whole genome, transcriptome and proteome sequencing can ensure the comprehensive collection of microscopic elements. EST: expressed sequence tags; DE: differential expression analysis; PWAS: proteome-wide association study. b. Modern equipments with AI enables high-throughput phenotyping. SVM: support vector machine; PCA: principal component analysis; RF: random forest; KNN: k-nearest neighbors; R-CNN: region-based convolutional neural network; Mamba: deep learning architecture focused on sequence modeling; SAM: segment anything model; CT: computed tomography.

High-throughput sequencing provides a potential solution for comprehensive genotyping. Sequencing technology has undergone several stages so far (Fig. S1a). The first generation sequencing methods, such as Sanger sequencing [1], can be applied only at specific regions of the genome. Sanger sequencing is time-consuming, costly and delivers only low throughput. Next-generation sequencing (NGS) [2],[3] addressed the challenges facing by earlier technologies. NGS technologies such as Illumina sequencing are renowned for their high-throughput, cost-efficiency with continuously improved accuracy, and they are still playing a pivotal role in genomics to date. A major drawback of NGS is in its read length (a few hundred bp), facing challenges when genotyping highly repetitive genomes. The third-generation sequencing (TGS) becomes popular with two main technologies, i.e., the single-molecule real-time sequencing technology by Pacific Biosciences (PacBio), which produces high-fidelity (HiFi) reads up to 15 kb with a base accuracy of 99% [4], and the nanopore sequencing technology by Oxford Nanopore Technologies (ONT), where a few reads can be up to Mb but with lower base accuracy [5]. TGS has become the mainstream approach for genome assembly, which improves the assembly continuity greatly [6],[7].

On the other hand, traditional genome assembly methods can only achieve pseudo-chromosomes that are with many gaps at repetitive genomic regions, for example, in rice, about 3-10% of genomic sequences are missing (or collapsed during assembly), which can make a FM construction less sensitive to the respective elements. Recently, the complete telomere to telomere (T2T) genome assembly was achieved in human [8], and the construction of pan-genome has become feasible with the decreased sequencing cost [9]. These advancements open doors to the FMLM construction with the complete set of genetic elements.

Further, genome assembly provides reference sequences for analyzing RNA, protein and epigenetic features through the respective sequencings, for which various methods have been developed (Fig. S1a) [10]-[12]. In addition to linear sequence assembly, the introduction of other sequencing technologies like Hi-C have enabled the analysis of long-distance interactions of genetic elements at structural level [13]. All these have been paving the way for collecting genetic elements essential for plant development accurately and comprehensively.

B. High-throughput phenotyping

Phenotype refers to morphological features observed from a crop species, which emerges from the non-linear interactions of all genetic elements (and the environment) [14]. Traditional plant phenotyping relies on manual measurement within a very limited number of samples, suffering from low efficiency and potential measurement errors. This is challenged by studies requiring large-scale phenotypes (for sufficient training of computational models), and it has become a bottleneck in developing novel breeding techniques [15]. Nowadays, leveraging equipments such as infrared cameras [16], sensors, unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) [17], and the Internet of Things (IoT) [18], multidimensional phenotypic data can be collected automatically and intelligently (Fig. S1b). Imaging technologies play an important role in this regard, which can be broadly categorized into three categories based on technologies involved, namely Visible Light Imaging (VLI), Spectral Imaging (SI), and Tomography.

The most widely used VLI technologies, employing RGB visible light cameras and fluorescence imaging, can be featured by low cost, non-destructive, real-time, high throughput, and versatility [19]. Commonly paired methods encompass color space transformations (Hue Saturation Value, HSV), texture extraction (Gray-Level Co-occurrence Matrix, GLCM; Histogram of Oriented Gradients, HOG), feature extraction, representation [20] and classification (Support Vector Machine, SVM; Artificial Neural Network, ANN). For instance, multi-modal

2D images (visible light, fluorescence, and near-infrared) were used for leaf counting [21], and color transformations and histogram intensity level segmentation were used for pest and disease identification [22].

Spectral Imaging (SI), employing multispectral and hyperspectral remote sensing techniques, captures spectral details across various wavelength bands including visible light, allowing for finer discrimination and identification of objects. In hyperspectral analysis, non-parametric methods like Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Support Vector Regression (SVR), Partial Least Squares Regression (PLSR), Random Forest (RF), and Neural Networks (NN) are widely used. For instance, PCA was applied in 57 spectral indices, revealing principal components that could be used to effectively detect diseases in tomato leaves [23].

Tomography, utilizing imaging techniques such as Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) and Computed Tomography (CT), along with image reconstruction and analysis, enables non-invasive underground phenotyping. This is particularly useful for analyzing tubers like *Solanum tuberosum*. It addresses issues of tissue damage and spatial distribution loss post-tissue washing [24]. MRI can provide high resolution and strong tissue-soil contrast, while CT offers finer spatial resolution for tissue examination. Integrating both technologies allows for a more thorough analysis of tissue characteristics across varying soil structures and moisture levels.

Beyond collecting phenotype data like images, analyzing the data presents another challenge. The analyses, such as image classification, object detection, and instance segmentation, require techniques from the field of computer vision (CV). Images can be classified by integrating visual features (e.g., color, texture) with machine learning methods such as KNN, PCA, NN. For example, convolutional neural network (CNN), using PyTorch and TensorFlow, was able to achieve highly accurate image classification on datasets like PlantVillage [25]. Object detection, using architectures like Faster R-CNN, SSD, and YOLO, showed good performance in disease detection and infection area localization in banana and tomato plants [26]. Instance segmentation, combined with genetic algorithms and other tools, facilitates detailed analysis of plant organs by measuring their dimensions [27].

Fig. S2. Foundation model overview, training strategy and applications. Language models have seen rapid development since the 20th century, from traditional natural language processing (NLP) tasks to more generalized, guided realistic tasks such as image and video generation. Underlying foundation models, various training strategies were developed, including fully fine-tuning, parameter-efficient fine-tuning, prompt tuning, and retrieval augmentation generation (RAG). In addition to conventional applications like question answering (Q&A), translation, and domain-specific document generation, text-to-image, text-to-video, and text-to-audio conversion can now be explored. These techniques have been applied across various sectors, including agriculture.

Integration of intelligent techniques into high-throughput phenotyping marks a notable advancement [28]. Further development of these technologies could collect and analyse the large-scale phenotype data required by Parallel Seeds.

C. Intelligent foundation model construction and training

In Parallel Seeds, the greatest challenge lies in associating genetic elements with phenotypes. To address this challenge, parallel theory and technologies can be adopted [29]-[31]. A parallel system consists of a real-world system and one or more artificial systems, where each artificial system is a digital representation of the real system [30]. The parallel system can establish a circular-causality feedback loop between the real system and artificial systems, enabling real-time dynamic comparison and analysis of their behaviours. Through extensive tests in the virtual world, parallel systems predict future states of the real system, and generate strategies for prescribing the real-world activities.

The kernel of artificial systems can adopt the emerging powerful FMs that can be constructed with training data together with the reinforcement learning from human feedback (RLHF) [32], satisfying CPSS. Recently, pre-trained language models (PLMs) utilizing transformer-based frameworks over extensive corpora were developed and laid the groundwork for large language models (LLMs), which have been widely used in different fields (Fig. S2). LLMs are exerting a profound influence on the AI community, and the introduction of FMs like *ChatGPT*, *GPT-4*, *Claude*, and *LLaMA2* etc. prompts a reconsideration of the potential for artificial general intelligence (AGI) [33].

FMs like LLMs show a great potential for uncovering the molecular language, i.e. the non-linear interactions among genetic elements and agronomic and economic traits [34]. With FI generated from FM, breeders can more accurately predict the features of offsprings of the genetic crosses of certain parental lines, thus reducing breeding cycles. Specifically, in crop breeding, a real plant in the physical space can be represented by FMs, and grow in parallel with it. To gain FI, FMs need to be trained on extensive data on genotypes, phenotypes and breeding knowledge such as various pathways involving genes controlling agronomic traits. This parallel paradigm follows circular causality and feedback control, where FMs can continuously improve FI regarding plant growth. After fine training, FMs can intelligently direct practical breeding based on computational simulations in the cyber space, such as the selection of parental lines for crosses to generate high-performance offsprings in the physical space.

It should be noted that existing FMs primarily focus on general language models or multimodal models that combine textual and image data. There is still an absence of FMs specifically designed for crop breeding, and there is a lack of specialization in foundation modelling for this specific domain. The central challenge of Parallel Seeds in this regard lies in the development and integration of methods capable of associating diverse types of breeding data, spanning multiple modes and scales. Another challenge lies in the extraction and explanation of the reasoning process of FMs, where methods also need to be developed.

SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURES

Fig. S3. PS-GPT: framework of foundation molecular language model (FMLM) for crop breeding. The integrated framework of PS-GPT consists of four sub-modules. Module I analyzes sequence corpus regarding DNA, RNA, methylation to produce cell-level representations using variational autoencoder (VAE) or Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) or convolutional neural network (CNN) etc. It can be designed for a wide range of predictive tasks such as gene expression prediction, cell type inference, SNP detection. It produces gene embeddings via interactions with a large language model using gene list prompt as input for GPT or LLAMA Api. Module II analyzes protein function corpus using variational autoencoder (VAE) or Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) or graph neural network (GNN) etc., performs tasks such as secondary tertiary structure prediction, functional prediction, cell type inference, and generates cell-specific tissue embeddings using protein list prompt as input for GPT or Llama Api. These embeddings aggregate into tissue-level features that can be combined with textual and visual data inputs in phenotype modules III and IV. Modality-specific encoders (bidirectional autoregressive network) in modules III and IV synthesize the inputs into a cohesive embedding. Together with chain of thoughts strategy (CoT) and finetuned GPT/Llama2/Claude as backbone, this entire process forms FMLM or PS-GPT, generating foundation intelligence from microscopic genotype and macroscopic phenotype information. Foundation intelligence provides optimal strategies for selective breeding. Following circular causality (from real to virtual and subsequently from virtual to real), foundation intelligence can be further improved with more breeding data.

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